

19

**Octrooi centrum
Nederland**

11

1044992

12 A OCTROOIAANVRAAG

21 Aanvraagnummer: **1044992**

51 Int. Cl.:

**C02F 1/32 (2025.01) H01J 65/00 (2025.01) H01J
61/04 (2025.01)**

22 Aanvraag ingediend: **12 november 2024**

62

30 Voorrang:
**6 februari 2024 NL 1044811
16 november 2023 NL 1044732**

71 Aanvrager(s):
Water Waves B.V. te Grou

41 Aanvraag ingeschreven:
22 mei 2025

72 Uitvinder(s):
**Mateo Jozef Jacques Mayer te Grou
Rene Martijn Wagterveld te Grou**

43 Aanvraag gepubliceerd:
23 mei 2025

74 Gemachtigde:
Geen

54 **Water purification device with electrodeless UV-C lamps and the powering thereof**

57 The present invention relates to a method and device for the purification of water, characterized by at least a first reactor with at least a first water inlet, a first water outlet, at least a first low pressure UV-C lamp without internal electrodes and without glow spiral, at least two electrodes operatively connected to the outer surface of said first low pressure UV-C lamp and a first hf frequency power supply. The first hf power supply automatically tunes the operating frequency of its end stage to the actual properties of said first low pressure UV-C lamp, thereby accounting for the changing lamp properties during start-up, changes in operating temperature and changes due to ageing of the lamp. The energy efficiency of the, at least two, electrodes, which are operatively connected to the outer surface of the first low-pressure UV-C lamp, is enhanced by roughening the outer lamp surface and / or a applying non conductive and / or a conductive coating to it, containing a large surface area of conductive particles. This measure increases the lamp's overall capacitance and decreases the required operating frequency of the hf power supply.

Water purification device with electrodeless UV-C lamps and the powering thereof

The present invention relates to a method and device for the purification of water, characterized by at least a first reactor with at least a first water inlet, a first water outlet, at least a first low pressure UV-C lamp without internal electrodes and without glow spiral, at least two electrodes operatively connected to the outer surface of said first low pressure UV-C lamp and a first hf frequency power supply. The first hf power supply automatically tunes the operating frequency of its end stage to the actual properties of said first low pressure UV-C lamp, thereby accounting for the changing lamp properties during start-up, changes in operating temperature and changes due to ageing of the lamp. The energy efficiency of the, at least two, electrodes, which are operatively connected to the outer surface of the first low-pressure UV-C lamp, is enhanced by roughening the outer lamp surface and / or applying a non conductive and / or a conductive coating to it, containing a large surface area of conductive particles. This measure increases the lamp's overall capacitance and decreases the required operating frequency of the hf power supply.

Introduction

Water purification by the use of UV-C irradiation is a generally applied technology for the disinfection of water without the use of chemicals. In combination with hydrogen peroxide and / or ozone, UV-C irradiation is also applied for the removal of micropollutants, such as medicine traces and pesticides, from drinking water and waste water through a process called advanced oxidation process (AOP). In this process, the UV-C irradiation is mainly used for the production of reactive radicals.

In principle, the use of UV-C irradiation is a very effective and energy efficient technology to purify drinking water and waste water from micro-organisms, genetic material carrying information on antibiotic resistance and micropollutants.

Unfortunately, the present UV-C technology, mainly comprising the use of low pressure UV-C lamps, also brings along several disadvantages:

- the UV-C disinfection lamps have a limited lifetime of typically two years or less mainly due to degeneration of the glow-spirals in the lamps.
- the UV-C power output of the lamps decreases during their lifetime because of evaporation of metals in the glow spiral and deposition of metal on the quartz inner surface of the lamps.
- frequently switching the lamps on and off results in faster degeneration of the glow spirals in the lamp and further reduces the lifetime of the lamps. This frustrates energy efficient use of the lamps.

In order to deal with these issues, several companies have developed low pressure UV-C lamps that are powered through induction. These lamps neither have internal electrodes,

nor a glow spiral, taking away the disadvantages of the classical tubular low pressure UV-C lamps with internal electrodes and glow spiral.

A low-pressure UV lamp powered by induction is typically housed in a square or rectangular enclosure consisting of a continuous glass tube positioned within this shape.

5 One or two induction coils are placed around the lamp to generate a magnetic field, which induces a current in the gas within the tube, causing it to emit UV radiation. The coils are strategically placed to ensure efficient energy transfer, and the current flows through them to create a magnetic field that excites the gas, allowing the lamp to emit light without direct electrical contact. Another type of induction lamp without internal electrodes features a coil
10 on a ferrite core, which is positioned within a low-pressure UV lamp shaped like a light bulb. The light bulb has an indentation where the ferrite coil is placed, ensuring the coil is operatively connected to the lamp to induce a current and produce UV radiation.

Unfortunately, these prior art induction UV lamps have a geometry that differs significantly from that of a straight tubular lamp with internal electrodes at both ends. The "square,
15 rectangular, or light bulb" shapes of induction UV lamps hinder their application in large-scale UV reactors for water purification. The size of the induction UV lamps and the relatively large coils, combined with the requirement for submersion and encapsulation in a quartz protective housing, make their use prohibitively expensive. Moreover, using lamps with a footprint different from the current straight tubular UV lamps poses significant reactor
20 design challenges. Existing disinfection reactors are specifically designed to ensure that each fluid element receives the necessary UV dose before exiting the system, and a non-tubular lamp footprint disrupts this arrangement. This is especially problematic as these reactors are often certified, and modifying them would necessitate new certification.

Retrofitting the vast number of UV reactors currently in use with induction lamps is virtually
25 impossible.

The technology of the present invention introduces a completely new, preferably straight cylindrical, low-pressure UV lamp concept that eliminates all the previously mentioned disadvantages of prior art UV lamps.

30

Technical description of the present invention

First, we will provide a general description of the technology according to the present invention, highlighting its advantages over prior art technology while mentioning the new inventive aspects and how they are interrelated. Following this, we will present an itemized
35 description of the technology, detailing different aspects and preferred embodiments of the invention.

The technology according to the present invention comprises a straight tubular low-

pressure UV lamp, typically made of quartz or glass, without internal electrodes in the light-emitting plasma region. A galvanically conductive electrode layer is attached to the UV lamp surface near both ends. This conductive layer is thin relative to the lamp's tube diameter, and the electrode surface area at each end is preferably kept small to maximize
5 the light-emitting surface area of the UV lamp.

The UV lamp is powered by a high frequency alternating current (AC) power source connected to the electrodes at both ends. Once ignited, the lamp functions as a lossy capacitor, with the quartz wall covered by electrodes acting as the dielectric and the plasma inside serving as a lossy conductor. This setup allows electrical energy from the high
10 frequency power source to transfer to the plasma inside the lamp, causing the lamp to emit UV radiation.

The inventors of the present technology found that the described UV lamp is highly inefficient. It requires extremely high voltage and frequency to transfer enough electrical energy for sufficient UV output that meets industrial standards. The limited surface area of
15 the electrodes, forming a lossy capacitor, results in low capacitance, hindering efficient operation. While the surface area can be increased by expanding the electrodes on the lamp, this comes at the cost of reducing the amount of UV power emitted. Consequently, the high-frequency power supply must operate in the MHz range and at a high voltage amplitude to power the plasma effectively. This leads to energy losses, electromagnetic
20 compatibility issues (with the lamp acting as an antenna), complex high-frequency power supply electronics, and the need for additional measures to comply with the EU directive on electromagnetic compatibility.

The inventors of the present technology found that the effective surface area of the electrodes, and therefore the capacitance of the lamp, could be increased by roughening
25 the electrode surface. This was achieved by methods such as sandblasting, followed by the application of conductive paint to the treated area. This approach proved effective in enhancing energy transfer and optimizing electrical lamp performance while increasing the emitted UV power at the same time.

The inventors of the present technology further investigated methods to increase the
30 surface area of the electrodes, thereby enhancing the lamp's capacitance. Remarkably, they found that the total capacitance of the lamp could be increased by a factor of 5 to 100 through specific measures:

- Applying a conductive coating containing conductive particles with a large specific surface area, which significantly increased the total surface area of the conductive
35 layer attached to the outer surface of the lamp.
- Applying a non-conductive coating embedded with conductive particles to the outer surface of the lamp, followed by a layer of conductive coating with high-surface-area

conductive particles. This combination effectively increased the total surface area of the conductive layer attached to the lamp's outer surface. An non limiting example of a feasible conductive coating is commercially available coating that is used to shield surface from electromagnetic radiation. Such coating typically contains a high concentration of galvanically conducting particles, such a metal particles, in the size range of nanometers, micrometers or millimeters.

The physics behind these improvements lies in the increase of the effective electrode surface area, which boosts the capacitance of the lamp. A larger surface area allows for greater charge accumulation, enhancing energy transfer and lamp efficiency by lowering the impedance between the power source and the plasma. In the case of the non-conductive coating with embedded conductive particles, the non-conductive matrix holds the conductive particles in a structured arrangement, creating microstructures that increase the roughness and surface area. When covered with a conductive layer, these microstructures provide more paths for current flow and charge storage, improving overall capacitance and energy transfer efficiency.

The inventors of the present invention also discovered that, due to the aforementioned measures to increase lamp capacitance, the high-frequency power supply can be significantly simplified, allowing its operating frequency to be chosen within the range of 20 kHz to 2 MHz depending on the lamp capacitance realized with the surface area increasing means. This patent application seeks protection for a new water purification reactor comprising at least one UV lamp according to the present invention and a high-frequency power supply that can be operatively connected to such a lamp.

For the sake of completeness, the advantages of the water purification reactor according to the present invention are outlined below:

- The lifetime of the new lamps in the reactor exceeds 6 years, compared to the typical 2-year lifespan of prior art lamps.
- Unlike UV lamps with internal electrodes, the new lamps can be switched on and off indefinitely without experiencing increased aging.
- The production cost of the new lamps is substantially lower than that of existing lamps, as they do not contain internal electrodes with glow spirals.
- The new lamps do not age, preventing performance degradation over time and ensuring better reactor performance with reduced maintenance.
- The reactor does not need to be oversized to compensate for performance loss due to issues like glow spiral decomposition and metal vapor deposits on the inner lamp surface, leading to up to 30% energy savings compared to prior art reactors.
- Due to the unique footprint of the electrodeless lamps described in the present

invention, existing reactors can be retrofitted with this technology, resulting in reduced maintenance and improved reactor performance.

With the basic principles of the technology according to the present invention explained and its advantages over prior art outlined, a first itemized list of aspects of the present invention will now be presented. It should be noted that this first list is based on new insights that are additive to and combinable with patent applications 1044732 and 1044811, which form the basis for this patent application and of which priority is claimed.

The first itemized list of aspects:

10 According to a first aspect, the present invention comprises a first straight low pressure UV lamp without inner electrode and without glow spiral.

According to a second aspect, the present invention comprises a first and a second galvanically conductive electrode operatively connected to a first and second outer surface area near the first end and the second end of the low pressure UV lamp respectively.

15 According to a third aspect, the present invention comprises means to increase the effective surface area of the first and second galvanically conductive electrodes. The means are chosen from the group of galvanically conductive particles with a high specific surface area that are operatively connected to the first and second outer surface area respectively. A non exhaustive list of galvanically conductive particles comprises metal
20 particles, any appearance form of carbon particles, preferably with a broad particle size distribution, conductive polymer particles and conductive coatings comprising any (combinations of) these particles.

Special embodiments of means to increase the effective surface area of the lamp electrodes are:

25 ● a roughened surface structure of the first and second electrode outer surface at both ends of the low pressure UV lamp, achieved through techniques such as sandblasting. This roughened surface structure serves as a means for enhancing surface area and contributes to improved performance by facilitating greater energy transfer.

30 ● a non conductive coating with encapsulated galvanically conductive particles applied on the first and second electrode outer surface at both ends of the low pressure UV lamp. The non conductive coating layer facilitates charge accumulation, thereby increasing the effective surface area of the electrodes. On top of this non conductive coating, a galvanically conductive layer of particles or
35 metal or carbon sheet is applied.

Any combination of the aforementioned means to increase the effective surface area of the lamp expressly makes part of the technology according to the present invention.

According to a fourth aspect the present invention consists of a water purification reactor with at least a first fluid inlet and a first fluid outlet.

According to a fifth aspect, the present invention consists of at least one at least partly submerged quartz protection sleeve in which at least one first straight low pressure UV

5 lamp is placed to isolate and protect it from the water to be purified.

According to a sixth aspect, the present invention comprises means to feed water into the reactor, such as a pump.

According to a seventh aspect, the present invention comprises a hf power supply, that is operating in the frequency range of the alternating current between 20 kHz en 2 MHz and operatively connected to the first and a second galvanically conductive electrodes of the

10

first straight low pressure UV lamp without inner electrode and without glow spiral.

Following practical implementations make expressly part of the present invention and are mentioned to give concrete non-limiting examples of conductive coating and non-conductive coatings containing particles that can be used in the framework of this

15

application.

We have following examples of conductive coatings:

1. A single-component, solvent-based acrylic lacquer formulated with high-purity nickel flakes as the conductive element. It adheres effectively to various substrates, including plastics such as ABS and polycarbonate, as well as wood and ceramics, due to a mild etching effect that integrates the coating with the substrate surface. The cured coating exhibits high abrasion resistance, excellent adhesion (rated 5B per ASTM D3359), and significant corrosion resistance, making it suitable for marine environments. Electrically, it provides a low volume resistivity of $0.004 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$ and surface resistances as low as $0.29 \Omega/\text{sq}$ at a thickness of 5.8 mil. The coating ensures effective EMI/RFI shielding across a broad frequency range, achieving attenuation levels of up to 74 dB at higher frequencies. The lacquer maintains durability under various environmental conditions, functioning continuously within a temperature range of -40°C to 120°C and withstanding intermittent temperatures up to 125°C .
2. A one-part acrylic lacquer containing high-purity silver flakes, designed for extreme conductivity and superior EMI/RFI shielding. This solvent-based formulation cures without the need for heat, resulting in a hard, smooth, and abrasion-resistant finish. The coating adheres strongly to plastics, including ABS and polycarbonate, as well as to wood and ceramics. It is characterized by an exceptionally low volume resistivity of $0.0001 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$, providing surface resistances of less than $0.01 \Omega/\text{sq}$ at minimum layer thicknesses of 0.9 mil. The material exhibits shielding attenuation exceeding 80 dB at frequencies up to 1 GHz and maintains effective performance at

20

25

30

35

higher frequencies. Its corrosion resistance is notable even under harsh marine conditions. The 842AR coating's mechanical properties include excellent adhesion (ASTM D3359 rating 5B) and a pencil hardness of 3H. It remains stable within a temperature range of -40°C to 120°C for continuous service and up to 125°C for intermittent use.

3. Conductive coatings containing nanometer sized particles i.e., particles with dimensions in the nanometer range from 1 nm to 1000 nm.
4. Conductive coatings containing micrometer sized particles i.e., particles with dimensions in the micrometer range from 1 micron to 1000 micron.
5. Conductive coatings containing millimeter sized particles i.e., particles in the millimeter range from 1 millimeter to 10 millimeter.
6. Conductive coatings containing any combination of nanometer and / or micrometer and / or millimeter sized particles.

A non-limiting example of a non-conductive coating according to the technology of the present invention, is an aerosol based conductive coating that is meant to be used for obtaining a conductive surface. However, the inventors of the present invention found that when the aerosol can, is not shaken properly, a coating with a concentration of metal particles is sprayed onto the surface that is still relatively high but too low for obtaining an electrical conductive layer for direct current. It appears that the non-conductive coating obtained in this way is very feasible as non-conductive coating according to the technology of the present invention. The coating that we used was the EMV 35 coating by the firm Kontakt Chemie with following properties: EMI 35 is an electrically conductive coating designed for plastic surfaces, comprising a thermoplastic resin matrix embedded with specialized copper pigments. These conductive pigments form an interlinked network within the resin, enabling the formation of an electrically conductive layer. This layer provides effective electromagnetic shielding, capable of reducing electromagnetic interference by up to 60 dB at a 50 μm coating thickness, as measured by ASTM ES 7-83. The coating demonstrates a surface resistivity of less than 0.5 Ω/sq at a 25 μm thickness. The cured film exhibits a copper-brown color, is thermally stable from -40°C to +95°C, and adheres effectively to various substrates. The formulation is designed for ease of application via aerosol, brush, or spray, with adjustments available for bulk use involving dilution and specialized spray systems.

Other examples are:

1. Non conductive coatings containing nanometer sized particles i.e., particles with dimensions in the nanometer range from 1 nm to 1000 nm.
2. Non - conductive coatings containing micrometer sized particles i.e., particles with dimensions in the micrometer range from 1 micron to 1000 micron.

3. Non conductive coatings containing millimeter sized particles i.e., particles in the millimeter range from 1 millimeter to 10 millimeter.
4. Non conductive coatings containing any combination of nanometer and / or micrometer and / or millimeter sized particles.

5 As already previously mentioned, this patent application claims priority from priority documents 1044732 and 1044811. For completeness, the text of these priority documents is included as part of this patent application, and the related second list of aspects is also additive to and combinable with the first itemized list. It is noted that any combination of any aspects is expressly included as part of the technology according to the present invention.

10 The second list of aspects:

According to a first aspect, the present invention relates to least a first, tubular, preferably cylindrical, low pressure UV light source, powered by capacitive energy transfer. Preferably, the first UV light source produces UV-C light but also UV lamps producing UVA and UVB light make part of the present invention. Figure 1 shows a non limiting example of a first UV light source according to the present invention. In the following, the operating principle of the first UV light source is explained by referring to the numbers (1) to (5) shown in figure 1. For the sake of clarity, it is noted that, in this patent application, the term UV-C light source is used in the description part of the application as a non-limiting example of a UV light source. For the sake of clarity, it is also noted that the terms conductive electrode or
15
20 conductive means relate to electrical conductive electrode and electrically conductive means, unless stated otherwise.

According to a second aspect, the present invention relates to a first, preferably flat, conductive electrode (1), operatively connected to the outer surface at one end of the low pressure chamber (5) of said first UV-C light source and a second, preferably flat,
25 conductive electrode (2) operatively connected to the outside surface at the other end of low pressure chamber (5) of said first UV-C light source. Preferably, the conductive electrodes are made of metal foil that is preferably attached to the outer surface of the first UV-C light source using conductive glue or conductive paint or a conductive coating or by winding metal foil around the first UV-C light source, thereby putting the foil under
30 mechanical stress, by stretching it during the winding procedure. Alternatively and even more preferably, the metal electrodes are produced by thermal metal deposition onto the outer surface of the first UV-C light source. Most preferably, the conductive electrodes are produced by carbon deposition using CVD (Chemical Vapor Deposition) and / or PVD (Physical Vapor Deposition) techniques, thereby achieving a graphite and / or graphene
35 coating that is known for its excellent electrical conductivity, mechanical strength and chemical stability.

According to a third aspect, the present invention relates to a hf (high frequency) power

supply, that is operatively connected to the first UV-C light source using electrical wires (3) and (4) in figure 1. The inventors of the technology described in the present patent application found that the hf power supply must have a number of very specific properties in order to successfully power the first UV-C light source. The hf power supply will now be described in detail and expressly makes part of the technology according to the present invention.

The hf power supply, shown in its most simple form in figure 2, consists of following specific elements that are crucial for its successful operation, that now will be listed and that will be discussed in more detail afterwards:

1. A frequency oscillator, that is preferably a Variable Frequency Oscillator (VFO), preferably operating in the frequency range between 1 MHz and 4 MHz, schematically shown in figure 2 as V2. Most preferably, the VFO is operated at a frequency around 2 MHz.
2. A high frequency N-channel power FET or N-FET cascode Q1 as switching device, preferably operating in the frequency range between 1 MHz and 4 MHz, together with C1 and L2 which are fictitious components accounting for parasitic capacitance mainly consisting of drain – source capacitance of the N-channel FET or cascode and a lump inductance parameter due to wiring on the PCB.
3. An RC circuit R2, R3, C4 comprising the replacement circuit of the first UV-C light source.
4. Tank circuit C2, L3, C3, L4, L5, C5 consisting of discrete L and C components. For a person skilled in the art, application of capacitor C5, parallel to the first UV-C light source, may seem redundant and undesired since it increases the current through the tank circuit and increases the voltage drop over the first UV-C light source per Watt required power input of the lamp. However, as will be explained later, the inventors of the technology in this patent application found that application of capacitor C5 is required to make the technology according to the present invention work at a sufficiently high power output so that it is a technically feasible alternative to prior art power supplies. Application of capacitor C5 in the circuit in figure 2 expressly makes part of the technology according to the present invention.

In the following, a number of electronic parts of the schematic in figure 2 will be discussed in more detail. Power source V1 is a DC voltage source, supplying the electrical power to light the UV-C lamp. V2 is an AC function generator, preferably producing a sinus with a preferable frequency around 2 MHz and an amplitude of preferably 5V to 15V. The AC function generator drives a hf N-channel FET driver that is feasible to be operated in the frequency range between 1 MHz and 4 MHz and preferably around 2 MHz. L1 is a choke.

C1 and L2 are fictitious parts to account for parasitic capacitance and inductance in the circuitry so that these were taken into account in model simulations. Components C2, L3, C3, L4, L5, C5 form a tank circuit causing the system to work as a robust kind of class EF amplifier to power the network R2, R3, C4, which is the equivalent circuit of the first UV-C light source.

In the equivalent circuit for the UV-C light source, R2 stands for the resistance of the glass or quartz of the first UV-C light source under the conductive electrodes that are attached to the outer surface of the lamp, C4 stands for the capacitance of the capacitor formed by the conductive electrodes with two layers of glass or quartz in between. The physical meaning of capacitor C4 is that, once gas discharge occurs in the lamp, a "lossy capacitor" is formed with two times the lamp wall thickness as dielectric since the conductive plasma in the lamp removes the "gas gap" in the capacitor. R3 accounts for the electrical losses in the plasma.

Figures 3 and 4 schematically show the simulated voltage drop over the drain of FET Q1 and the voltage drop over both electrodes of the first UV-C light source, as simulated with the LTSpice software package, respectively. The curves were obtained with following values, that can be seen as a non-limiting example of the technology according to the present invention: V1=95 Volt, V2=10V amplitude @ 2 MHz, dutycycle=0.3, C1=1 nF, L2=2 nH, C2=2.2 nF, L3=1 μ H, C3=2.59 nF, L4=3.3 μ H, L5=9.05 μ H, R2=220 kOhm, C4=80 pF, R1=360 Ohm, C5=620 pF. These values are for driving a 75 Watt tubular UV-C lamp. The simulated amplitude of the voltage over the drain and source of the N-channel FET in figure 3 was about 360V maximum. The simulated amplitude of the resulting AC voltage over the lamp electrodes was about 470 Volt.

Although it is possible to simulate and validate the desired behavior of the schematic in figure 2, the inventors of the technology in this patent application found that building and operating the electrical circuit in figure 2 and connecting it to a 75 Watt UV-C lamp with conductive electrodes on both ends, according to the present invention, thereby replacing circuit R2, R3, C4 with the lamp, results in a complete failure of the power supply system for a myriad of reasons.

After a long research trajet, the inventors of the technology in this patent application found that there is a very specific operating window of electrical conditions, combined with a very specific design of the electrical circuit and several electronic parts in the circuit, at which the power supply in figure 2 performs surprisingly well to operate a first UV-C light source without internal electrodes and with capacitive electrodes mounted on the outside wall of the lamp.

The operating window to successfully apply the power supply in figure 2 will now be described in detail through an itemized list of measures and expressly makes part of the technology according to the present invention.

5

Following measures must be taken to successfully apply the technology according to the present invention in practise:

1. The frequency at which the amplifier at figure 2 is operated must be in the range of 1 MHz to 4 MHz. If the operating frequency is too high i.e., above 4 MHz,
10 electromagnetic compatibility issues with the schematic in figure 2 will occur. Additionally, parasitic capacitities and inductance introduced by the wires to the first UV-C light source, the discrete parts and traces on the PCB and the direct environment in which the first UV-C light source is present, e.g., in quartz protection sleeves submerged under water inside of a UV-C reactor, will make the power
15 supply to operate unreliably or fail. If the operating frequency is too low, the amount of energy per square meter of electrode area that can pass through the capacitive electrodes on the first UV-C light source, i.e., the conductive electrodes, is too low. In practise this means that a too large part of the first UV-C light source must be covered by conductive electrodes resulting in only a very small light producing
20 window of the UV-C light source, which is inefficient from an energy point of view.
2. Capacitor C5 must be applied in the schematic in figure 2 and must conduct a significant current although it is connected in parallel with the first UV-C light source. In spite of the fact that capacitor C5 shortcircuits a significant part of the current that is available to flow through the first UV-C light source, electrical losses can be
25 limited by applying a high quality capacitor with very limited dielectric losses. Although contra-intuitive, capacitor C5 must be applied to load the circuit in figure 2 with sufficient capacitance. Omitting capacitor C5 will, at first sight, increase the efficiency of the power supply. However, since the capacitance of the first UV-C light source is very limited, very small capacitance changes in the load of the power
30 supply e.g., parasitic capacitance changes due to changes in position of the wires to the lamp or changes in the lamp environment, will result in unstable performance of both the power supply and the first UV-C light source. In several of the many experiments that were executed with the schematic in figure 2 and where capacitor C5 was omitted, only approaching the first UV-C light source with a hand, without
35 touching the light source, resulted in a parasitic capacitance that changed the load of the power supply to such extent that the N-channel FET was overloaded and broke down. It is noted that applying capacitor C5 parallel to the first UV-C light

source results in a higher voltage over the conductive electrodes attached to the outer surface of the first UV-C light source per Watt required power input to the lamp. This is acceptable since dielectric losses in the glass or the quartz of the first UV-C light source are limited.

- 5 3. The first and second conductive electrodes, attached to the outer surface on each end of the first UV-C light source respectively, must be attached to the lamp surface through a conductive glue or a conductive coating or through CVD and / or PVD or through winding the conductor around the lamp under mechanical stretch conditions. This is required to achieve a "lamp capacitance C4" in figure 2 with
- 10 sufficiently low dielectric losses to operate the first UV-C light source in an energy efficient way and to prevent the first and second conductive electrodes to become too hot. Additionally, at very high power conditions, at least on of the
- 15 beforementioned methods to apply the conductive electrodes onto the outer surface area of the first UV-C light source is required to prevent the formation of gas discharge (a corona) in small air gaps between the conductive layer and the
- construction material of the first UV-C light source, which is usually glass or quartz. For the sake of clarity, it is noted that the first and second conductive electrodes do neither comprise nor form a coil.
- 20 4. The AC function generator V2 must be equipped with means to vary its frequency in order to smoothly correct for changing load properties during start-up and during ageing of the first UV-C light source. Since the first UV-C light source does not contain internal electrodes with glow spiral, its start-up will be cold i.e., without preheating. As a consequence, the impedance of the plasma in the lamp R3 will decrease considerably during the start-up and warming up period, resulting in a
- 25 lamp load that changes over time. Although ageing of the first UV-C light source will be very limited i.e., its lifetime will be in the order of 6 years or longer, the load properties of the lamp will slowly change over time. One reason for the slowly changing load properties of the lamp is the ageing of the dielectric between the conductive electrodes i.e., the glass or quartz wall. As a result of dielectric wear,
- 30 dielectric losses in the "lamp capacitor C4" will increase, resulting in a decrease of R2 which on its turn changes the load of the lamp. The power supply in figure 2 was designed for its extremely high energy efficiency. A disadvantage brought along by the design is its high sensitivity for a change in load properties. Any change in the apparent capacitive load of the lamp i.e., in the R2, R3, C4 equivalent network, will
- 35 change the resonant frequency of the power supply - first UV-C light source combination. If, in such case, the AC function generator V2 is not fine tuned to produce a signal with the resonant frequency of the power supply - first UV-C light

source combination, the power supply will be very inefficient or break down due to overheating.

A concrete non-limiting example of means to automatically vary the frequency of AC function generator V2 depending on the load of the first UV-C light source will now be given. From the lamp equivalent network R2, R3, C4, we know that the apparent capacity of the lamp at startup is too low and its internal resistance too high. This results in the resonant frequency of the final stage being higher at startup than in the steady state, i.e., after the lamp warms up. We also know the resonant frequency of the final stage in the steady state, which preferably is 2 MHz.

Therefore, during the lamp's warming-up process, the resonant frequency of the final stage decreases from a value X, greater than 2 MHz, to the steady state value of 2 MHz. We have thus solved our startup problem by starting the control frequency at X and then decreasing it according to the lamp's startup characteristics to 2 MHz. This reduces the startup problem to how to easily synchronize the control frequency with the resonant frequency of the final stage. The inventors of the present patent application have devised several solutions and will focus here on the simplest and most practical ones, without limiting the extend of the technology to the examples given. By applying a function generator V2 with a VFO (Variable Frequency Oscillator), we can achieve a voltage-controlled frequency for the control. Suitable VFO chips include the LTC6909 and the AD9837, with frequency resolutions of 19.42 Hz (via a Digital to Analogue Converter i.e., a DAC) and 5 Hz (via serial programming), respectively. This provides a capacity correction resolution per frequency step around 2 MHz in a tank circuit with a capacity around 700 pF of 0.014 pF and 0.0035 pF respectively, which is excellent. If we choose the LTC6909, we can directly control it with a DAC. By placing a light sensor or a temperature sensor on the UV-C lamp, which emits a light intensity-dependent or temperature-dependent voltage, we can automatically program the LTC6909. For example, if we take the lamp temperature as the criterion, we adjust the DAC linked to the temperature sensor so that it transmits the voltage to the LTC6909 corresponding to a control frequency of 2 MHz at operating temperature and a voltage for a control frequency X, greater than 2 MHz, at temperatures below 20 degrees. Between 20 degrees and operating temperature, we gradually decrease the control frequency from X to 2 MHz as the temperature increases. The value of X depends on the type of lamp and the surface area of the conductors around the lamp and can be determined experimentally. If a light sensor is used to optimize the operating frequency of the first UV-C light source - power supply combination, we use the observation that the first UV-C light source produces most light if the function

generator V2 produces a frequency that exactly matches the resonant frequency of the system. This means that we can apply a light sensor that measures continuously and automatically the light output of the first UV-C light source together with a microcontroller that changes the frequency of function generator V2 with a very small step, measures the light output again and decides whether or not to switch back to the original value or keep the new frequency value. By the use of the microcontroller and a feed back loop to function generator V2, the first UV-C light source can be operated continuously at the optimum frequency. The minimum acceptable frequency output of V2 and the maximum acceptable frequency output of V2 are set in the microcontroller and if the lamp cannot be operated at the desired light intensity within the pre-programmed frequency range, the power supply will automatically switch off to prevent any damage to the electronics and the first UV-C light source and generate an alarm. For the sake of clarity it is noted that the AC function generator V2 may consist of a microcontroller or an embedded electronics chip equipped with functionality to produce a hf signal with a frequency between 1 MHz and 4 MHz. For the sake of clarity, it is also noted that current sensors, e.g., sensors measuring the current through the lamp and / or the current through a discrete part of the hf power supply, or voltage sensors e.g., sensors measuring the voltage over the lamp and / or the voltage over a discrete electronic part of the hf power supply can also be used to optimize and adjust the operating frequency of the hf power supply to the resonant frequency of the hf power supply - first UV-C light source combination.

5. The duty cycle of the signal produced by frequency generator V2 that is used to switch the N-Channel FET or cascode must be significantly smaller than 0.5 i.e., typically within the range of 0.20 to 0.40. One way to achieve this duty cycle in a reproducible way at frequencies in the 2 MHz range is to use a function generator V2 that produces a sinus or sinusoid signal with an amplitude in the range between 5 to 10 Volt and apply a RC network load to this signal such that the threshold voltage for the N-Channel FET or cascode driver chip is achieved at a duty cycle in the range between 0.20 to 0.40. In other words: we produce a sinus or sinusoid signal and shave the peaks of this signal at such a level that we end up with a signal that switches the FET driver chip at a duty cycle between 0.20 and 0.40. This method expressly makes part of the current invention since we observed that this approach makes it possible to easily meet the electromagnetic compatibility regulations, contrary to methods using a square wave to set the duty cycle. An explanation for this observation is that square wave signals consist of odd harmonics that cause electromagnetic compatibility issues. For the sake of clarity, it is noted that a

microcontroller or embedded electronics chip may contain the functionality of the AC frequency generator V2 and / or the electronic circuit to convert the hf signal into a signal with a duty cycle between 0.2 and 0.4 and / or the FET driver.

6. At least any of the coils L1, L3, L4 and L5, preferably at least two of them, more preferably at least three of them and most preferably at least L3, L4 and L5 must have a spiral wound configuration in the form of flat traces on a PCB in order to deal with the high currents through these coils at frequencies near 2 MHz and the resulting large skin effect. The design of the amplifier in figure 2 leads to high currents in the tank circuit C2, L3, C3, L4, L5, C5 and the first UV-C light source (R2, C4, R3). Especially, application of capacitor C5 to this circuit, which is required in the technology according to the present invention, considerably increases the current through the capacitors and coils in this network. For the capacitors, this does not cause any issues since we can apply high voltage capacitors with very low dielectric losses. The coils present a serious challenge due to the skin effect, which causes current to predominantly travel along the exterior of the coil's conductor. This results in considerable Ohmic losses within the coils and leads to excessive heat production. For the power supply shown in figure 2, it appears that the required copper wire coils would need to be very large. However, coils of such size are not commonly available commercially, and their substantial geometrical footprint would render the power supply impractically large and not cost-effective for implementation. A possible solution to apply coils with a ferrite core was considered, since these coils need substantially less windings, but application of these coils bring along serious drawbacks as well, especially at frequencies as high as 2 Mhz: there would be substantial core losses, increased Eddy currents, reduced inductance and, although the required conductor length for the coil is shorter as compared to an air coil, the skin effect would still affect the coil performance as well. The inventors of the technology in the present patent application found that the application of spiral wound coils through flat traces on a PCB are very feasible for application in the power supply in figure 2. Figure 4 shows an example of such a PCB with three spiral wound coils on it. Since the coil consists of traces with a very large outer surface, the skin effect has only a small impact on the coil performance. Additionally, the footprint of the coils is extremely small since the PBC with the coils can be stacked with the PCB containing of the power supply shown in figure 2, thereby reducing the footprint of the coils to nearly zero. Another advantage of the spirally wound coils on the PCB is the very large surface area of the coils, resulting in very good heat transfer of energy dissipated in the coils to the surrounding environment. This makes the coils on the PCB very feasible for both heat transfer

through passive cooling, using a housing for the electronics with cooling holes, and forced cooling through application of a ventilator in the housing. Application of spiral wound coils makes expressly part of the technology according to the present invention. For the sake of clarity, it is noted that, in case the flat coils are on a separate PCB, they need to be connected to the end stage of the power supply. This is done by the use of pieces of flat copper sheet instead of copper wire in order to suppress the skin effect. This approach expressly makes part of the technology according to the present invention.

Now that the most important properties of the first UV-C light source and its power supply have been explained, a number of preferred embodiments of the technology according to the present invention will be discussed.

In a first preferred embodiment, the technology according to the present invention is applied in a water purification reactor to remove micropollutants i.e., pesticides and / or medicine traces from water and / or to disinfect water through advanced oxidation and / or to remove genetic material coding for antibiotic resistance from the water. For this purpose at least one first UV-C light source is installed in a reactor with a fluid inlet and a fluid outlet. Inside the reactor, a tubular quartz protection sleeve is placed in such a way that it is submerged in the water. The first UV-C light source is placed inside the quartz protection sleeve so that it is not in direct contact with the water. The first UV-C light source is operatively connected to a power supply according to the present invention. It is noted that a water purification reactor with internal quartz protection sleeves is commonly applied in the water purification industry. In the prior art water purification reactor, conventional low pressure UV-C lamps with internal glow spirals and electrodes are applied together with conventional power supplies. Since the UV-C lamps according to the present invention have the same geometrical footprint as the conventional UV-C lamps, prior art UV-C reactors can be improved through retrofitting them with first UV-C light sources and power supplies according to the present invention. A water purification reactor with a fluid inlet, a fluid outlet, quartz protection sleeves, a first UV-C light source and its power supply, expressly makes part of the technology according to the present invention.

In a second preferred embodiment, the technology according to the present invention is applied in a batchwise operated water purification reactor for the removal of micropollutants from water through advanced oxidation. In this application the batch reactor contains at least one first UV-C light source operatively connected to a power supply according to the present invention. Preferably, the batch reactor is also equipped with means for the dosing of hydrogen peroxide and / or ozone as a reactant in the advanced oxidation process.

In a third preferred embodiment, the technology according to the present invention is applied in low pressure tubular light sources producing visible light, UV-A light, UV-B light and UV-C light i.e., in light sources producing light in the wavelength range of 230 nm to 800 nm.

5 A fourth preferred embodiment comprises a water purification reactor according to the present invention where other light sources than UV-C light sources are applied i.e., UV-A light, UV-B light or visible light. It is noted that in the claims the term UV light source is used. In this patent application the term UV light source stands for a light source selected from the group of low pressure UV-C, UV-B and UV-A light sources. This patent application
10 was written with a "first UV-C light source" as the default low pressure UV light source equipped with conductors on the outer surface of the lamp. In case the term UV light source is used, it can be a first UV-C light source, a first UV-B light source and a first UV-A light source. Optionally a photo catalyst is applied to convert the light into OH radicals or oxygen radicals. Non limiting examples of photocatalysts are: methylene blue, TiO₂.

15 In a fifth preferred embodiment, the technology according to the present invention is applied in air disinfectors. Besides the long lifetime of the lamps, the high energy efficiency of the technology the lamps are also insensitive to frequently switching them on and off, which also brings along possibilities to save energy and cost for replacing the lamps.
In a sixth preferred embodiment, the technology according to the present invention is
20 applied in lamps with other shapes than linear low pressure vacuum tubes, such as glow bulbs and bended tubes such as squares and circles.

In a seventh preferred embodiment, the technology according to the present invention comprises coaxial cables to connect the first hf power supply with the first UV-C light source. The advantage of applying coaxial cables is, amongst others, that the
25 electromagnetic compatibility regulations can be met more easily.

In an eighth preferred embodiment, the technology according to the present invention is combined with ultrasound to keep the quartz protection sleeves in the water purification reactor clean.

In a ninth preferred embodiment, the energy efficiency of the technology according to the present invention is substantially improved by increasing the capacitance of the electrodes
30 that are attached onto the outer surface of the UV-C light source. To achieve this, the outer surface, of the first low-pressure UV-C lamp, is enhanced by roughening its outer surface at the location where the external electrodes are attached to the lamp surface. This increases the effective electrode surface area, and as a consequence, the lamp's overall capacitance.

35 A higher effective capacitance of the lamp's outer electrodes, results in a lower voltage drop across the capacitor formed by the electrodes and the lamp's dielectric at the same current through the lamp. This will enhance the energy efficiency of both the lamp's power supply

and the UV-C light source, due to reduced dielectric losses in the capacitors and coils at the power supply's end stage, as well as lower dielectric losses in the lamp itself.¹² An effective way to roughen the outer surface of the UV-C light source, that is usually made of glass or quartz, is to sandblast the outer surface of the lamp where the electrodes are to be attached. Selecting the diameter of the sand particles allows for the adjustment of the total effective surface area of the electrodes to a specific target value. Using smaller particles in the sandblasting process will increase the effective surface area of the electrodes per square centimeter on the previously flat surface of the lamp cylinder. After executing the sand blasting procedure, the at least two conductive electrodes need to be operatively connected to the sand blasted surface area. A very efficiency way to achieve a good coating between conductor and increased surface area is physical vapor deposition (PVD) or similar process. Alternatively, a conductive coating, such as the electrically conductive paint commonly used in the electronics industry, can be applied to the roughened surface area. These techniques expressly make part of the technology according to the present invention. Now the technology has been explained in detail, it is noted that increasing the effective outer surface of the electrodes does not increase the inner surface of the quartz or glass body of the UV-C light source. Surprisingly, the inventors of the present invention found that it is not required to increase the lamp's inner surface area. Without limiting the extend of the technology according to the present invention, the inventors have following explanation for this observation. The charge transfer from electrons and ions in the lamp's plasma to the inner surface of the lamp exclusively depends on the collision frequency of these charged particles with the surface of the lamp's body. The collision frequency on its turn depends on the lamp's properties in terms of gas composition, gas pressure and dimensions of the lamp and the current through the lamp. At practical operating conditions of the lamp, the collision frequency of charged particles with the lamp's internal body surface is not limiting the capacitor formed by the electrodes attached onto the outer lamp surface. The limiting factor appears to be surface charge that can be present on the outer electrodes attached onto the outer lamp's surface. As a result, increasing the effective capacitor surface area of the outer conductors attached to the lamp surface, will increase the overall capacitance of the lamp. It is noted that sandblasting is one of many techniques to roughen the surface of the outer body of the lamp. Other techniques, not limiting the scope of the invention and expressly making part of the current invention include laser ablation, chemical etching (for example, treating the surface with hydrogen fluoride), mechanical roughening, and plasma etching.

35 Clauses:

1. Water purification reactor characterized by:

- a reaction vessel with at least one liquid inlet, one liquid outlet, and means to pump

- water into the reactor, containing
- at least one quartz protective tube,
 - which is at least partially submerged in the water to be treated and
 - contains at least one tubular low-pressure UV light source without internal
- 5 electrodes and without a glow spiral, equipped with
- a first conductive electrode attached to the outer surface of one end of the said first UV light source, and
 - a second conductive electrode attached to the outer surface of the other end of the said first UV light source, wherein
- 10 ● the first and second conductive electrodes consist at least partially of electrically conductive means selected from the group of electrically conductive adhesives, electrically conductive paints, electrically conductive coatings, metal particles, metal foils, graphite, and graphene, and wherein
- the first and second electrodes do not contain a coil and do not form a coil,
- 15 ● means to increase the effective surface area of the first and second conductive electrodes,
- a high-frequency amplifier operatively connected to the first and second electrodes, characterized by
 - an operating frequency of the alternating current through the lamp in the range of 20
- 20 kHz to 2 MHz.
2. Water purification reactor according to claim 1, wherein the means to increase the effective surface area of the first and second conductive electrodes consist of a roughened surface structure on the outer surface of the lamp on which the first and second electrodes are applied.
- 25 3. Water purification reactor according to any of the preceding claims 1 and 2, further comprising means to increase the effective surface area of the first and second conductive electrodes, consisting of a non-galvanically conductive coating containing conductive particles, upon which a second galvanically conductive layer is applied.
4. Water purification reactor according to any of the preceding claims 1 to 3, wherein the
- 30 means to increase the effective surface area of the first and second conductive electrodes include a galvanically conductive layer of individual galvanically conductive particles with a large specific surface area.
5. Water purification reactor according to any of the preceding claims 1 to 4, further comprising a first capacitor connected in parallel with the first tubular UV light source.
- 35 6. Water purification reactor according to any of the preceding claims 1 to 5, characterized in that at least one of the coils in the high-frequency amplifier is a spiral-wound coil that is part of a PCB.

7. Water purification reactor according to any of the preceding claims 1 to 6, further comprising first means to automatically tune the operating frequency of the first high-frequency amplifier to the instantaneous resonant frequency of the first high-frequency amplifier–first light source combination, characterized in that the first means include at least
5 one sensor selected from the group of temperature sensors, light sensors, current sensors, and voltage sensors.

8. Water purification reactor according to any of the preceding claims 1 to 7, wherein the UV light source produces UV-C radiation.

For completeness, the formulation described in the abstract is hereby also included in the
10 description: The present invention relates to a method and device for the purification of water, characterized by at least a first reactor with at least a first water inlet, a first water outlet, at least a first low pressure UV-C lamp without internal electrodes and without glow spiral, at least two electrodes operatively connected to the outer surface of said first low pressure UV-C lamp and a first hf frequency power supply. The first hf power supply
15 automatically tunes the operating frequency of its end stage to the actual properties of said first low pressure UV-C lamp, thereby accounting for the changing lamp properties during start-up, changes in operating temperature and changes due to ageing of the lamp. The energy efficiency of the, at least two, electrodes, which are operatively connected to the outer surface of the first low-pressure UV-C lamp, is enhanced by roughening the outer
20 lamp surface and / or a applying non conductive and / or a conductive coating to it, containing a large surface area of conductive particles. This measure increases the lamp's overall capacitance and decreases the required operating frequency of the hf power supply.

25

30

35

Conclusies

1. Waterzuiveringsreactor gekenmerkt door
 - een reactievat met tenminste een vloeistofinlaat, een vloeistofuitlaat en middelen om water in de reactor te pompen met daarin
 - 5 ● tenminste een kwartsbeschermhuis
 - die tenminste ten dele is ondergedompeld in het te behandelen water en die
 - tenminste een eerste buisvormige lage druk UV lichtbron zonder interne elektrode en zonder gloeispiraal bevat en is uitgerust met
 - 10 ● een eerste geleidende elektrode die is aangebracht op het buitenoppervlak van een uiteinde van genoemde eerste UV lichtbron en
 - een tweede geleidende elektrode die is aangebracht op het buitenoppervlak van het andere uiteinde van genoemde eerste UV lichtbron waarbij
 - de eerste en de tweede geleidende elektrode tenminste gedeeltelijk bestaan uit elektrische geleidende middelen uit de groep van elektrisch geleidende lijmen, elektrisch geleidende verven, elektrisch geleidende coatings, metaaldeeltjes, metaalfolies, grafiet en grafeen en waarbij
 - 15 ● de eerste en tweede elektrode geen spoel bevatten en ook geen spoel vormen,
 - middelen om het effectieve oppervlak van de eerste geleidende elektrode en de tweede geleidende elektrode te vergroten,
 - 20 ● een hf versterker die werkzaam verbonden is met de eerste en tweede elektrode, gekarakteriseerd door
 - een werfrequentie van de wisselstroom door de lamp in het gebied van 20 kHz tot 2 MHz.
2. Waterzuiveringsreactor volgens conclusie 1 waarbij de middelen om het effectieve oppervlak van de eerste geleidende elektrode en de tweede geleidende elektrode te vergroten bestaan uit een verruwde oppervlaktestructuur van het buitenoppervlak van de lamp waarop de eerste elektrode en de tweede elektrode zijn aangebracht.
- 25 3. Waterzuiveringsreactor volgens een van de voorgaande conclusies 1 en 2 vermeerderd met middelen om het effectieve oppervlak van de eerste en tweede geleidende elektrode te vergroten bestaande uit een niet galvanisch geleidende coating die geleidende deeltjes bevat en waarop een tweede galvanisch geleidende laag is aangebracht.
- 30 4. Waterzuiveringsreactor volgens een van de voorgaande conclusies 1 t/m 3 waarbij de middelen om het effectieve oppervlak van de eerste en tweede geleidende elektrode te vergroten een galvanisch geleidende laag van individuele galvanisch geleidende deeltjes betreft.
- 35 5. Waterzuiveringsreactor volgens een van de voorgaande conclusies 1 t/m 4

vermeerderd met een eerste condensator die parallel is geschakeld aan de eerste buisvormige UV lichtbron.

- 5
6. Waterzuiveringsreactor volgens een van de voorgaande conclusies 1 t/m 5 met het kenmerk dat tenminste een van de spoelen in de hf versterker een spiraalgewonden spoel die onderdeel uitmaakt van een PCB,
7. Waterzuiveringsreactor volgens een van de voorgaande conclusies 1 t/m 6 vermeerderd met eerste middelen om de werkfrequentie van de eerste hf versterker automatisch af te stemmen op de momentane resonantiefrequentie van de eerste hf versterker - eerste lichtbron combinatie met het kenmerk dat de eerste middelen
- 10 tenminste een sensor bevatten uit de groep van temperatuursensors, lichtsensors, stroomsensors en spanningssensors.
8. Waterzuiveringsreactor volgens een van de voorgaande conclusies 1 t/m 7 waarbij de UV lichtbron UV-C straling produceert.
- 15
- 20
- 25
- 30
- 35

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Fig. 5